

Original Research Article

“Open your eyes, and then open your eyes again:”¹ An Autoethnography of a Mathematics Educator with Undiagnosed ADHD

Rebecca A. Norton²
Massachusetts Maritime Academy

ABSTRACT: I started attending school early at my mom’s preschool, so maybe I was fulfilling some predetermined destiny when I finally became a teacher myself. To me, though, it was more serendipitous; I never wanted to be a teacher. I was an independent woman intent on following my interests and opportunities. The path to earning my PhD in Mathematics Education was filled with twists and roadblocks, all of which have made me a better mathematics educator. I am good at what I do,³ but I think I could be better. As it turns out, after doing the reflection and data mining required of an autoethnographer, I have realized that I have not been as independent as I thought. For the first time in my life, with extra demands and without the support I have grown accustomed to, I am struggling. Supporting myself and my neurodivergent family is a challenge. I think I have ADHD, but it is hard to convince my therapist when I have accomplished so much, especially since she does not know how much my family has helped me along the way. So, I remain undiagnosed. “If she is a true hag, she’ll find a way hersel’. We all ha’ to dree our weird. Whatever’s out there, she’s got to face it. If she canna, she’s no true hag” (Pratchett, 2005, p. 301). I see myself in my daughter, and I want to provide her with similar scaffolding to what I received as a child, but I also want to allow her to be true to herself. Ironically, it is the work of becoming and being a mathematics educator that has provided me with the most insight into my struggles. Conversely, it is my background, and I think my ADHD brain, that has made me such a strong educator. The realizations I have made in this autoethnographic journey have been my call to action to help support neurodivergent students and educators, including my daughter and myself.

KEYWORDS: *ADHD, mathematics education, autoethnography, feminism, giftedness*

¹ (Pratchett, 2005, p. 308)

² Rebecca A. Norton (she/her) began writing this autoethnography while she was a doctoral candidate at University of Massachusetts Dartmouth. She is currently an Associate Professor in the Science & Mathematics Department at Massachusetts Maritime Academy. Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to 101 Academy Drive, Buzzards Bay, MA 02532. Email: rnorton@maritime.edu <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0349-8946>

³ “Good with the herbs, are you?”

“No, I’m very good with the herbs.”

“Oh, there’s a bit of swank, eh?” said Nanny.

“If I didn’t know I was good with herbs, I’d be stupid, Mrs. Ogg” (Pratchett, 2007d, p. 747).

Getting started is not always easy for me. I have mostly done well to overcome the inertia necessary to begin something, but it was not until recently that I understood the power of having someone else provide that prompting. For, once I start something, I generally accomplish it. When I am focused, I am creative, resourceful, and productive. I am so productive that, for most of my life, I was unaware that sometimes I have difficulty focusing. I can reflect on my life now and think about times when I have had difficulty but, for the most part, in the midst of it all, the supports that existed within my family and community were all in the right places, allowing me to flourish without even realizing I was getting help. With my “invisible” support, I have accomplished some interesting, unusual, and difficult things in my lifetime. Alas, finding the momentum necessary to complete this project has been hard. I am thankful to have had some help along the way.

I began my autoethnography in 2015 while I was still in my PhD program at the University of Massachusetts Dartmouth. I had a phenomenal professor, Dr. Jesse Bazzul, for a course in “Special Topics in Math Education.” As our main project, we constructed autoethnographies by consulting Denzin’s (2013) publication *Interpretive Autoethnography* and providing each other with peer feedback. At the end of the semester, I received helpful comments from Dr. Bazzul on what I might do to prepare mine for publication. I was flattered by the suggestion and wanted to have something published, but I had a dissertation to write, career choices to make, a wedding to plan, a baby to welcome—and life just happened without my ever doing anything with my paper. That is, until a call for submissions appeared in my inbox as part of a post on the NE-COMMIT website, an organization with which I am active, and I remembered my paper. I wavered about submitting it but ultimately reasoned that other than the potential sting of rejection, I did not have much to lose. “Where this takes me, there I choose to go, she told herself...I choose. This I choose to do” (Pratchett, 2007, p. 865). I was pleasantly surprised when the founding editor, Dr. Alexander Moore, responded with interest. I told him that I had written it several years ago for a class project and that it did not feel quite complete. He offered me an option to work with a mentor, and I am thankful for accepting it. Dr. Kyle Whipple, who had recently written an autoethnography for JTM-ME, agreed to help guide me as I crafted mine. Coach Whipple was just the person I needed to provide the support to help me do my best work. Having been through the process himself, he recognized the emotional rollercoaster of writing an autoethnography as well as the potential of my ideas—in all the scattered ways I presented them during our Zoom sessions—as I slowly built up the courage to get started and work through the tears that so many of my memories evoked. Here I am, several months later than I thought I would be, ready to tell my story. I know, now, that I could not have done it alone.

Literature Review

To me, writing a literature review is always the hardest part of a paper, and I was tempted to use the flexible and creative license of autoethnography (Poulos, 2021) to skip it. However, I did not want to let the professors from my PhD program down; they had taught me well. So, I imposed some organization on my process to ensure I would not get too far off-track. To start, I decided only to consult articles that were published within the last ten years. Any references in my work that precede 2015 were part of my original writing I

did as a PhD student. Second, because I was writing an autoethnography, I suspected several themes that would eventually emerge, made a list of topics, and contained my research to those topics. Coach Whipple told me to think of it as a literature paragraph, and that seemed less daunting. So, below is a short section on what I perceive as the relevant literature.

A Relevant Discussion of ADHD

The definition and diagnosis of Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) continues to evolve (Barnes et al., 2017). From a medical perspective, ADHD is a neurodevelopmental disorder with sources varying on its prevalence (Canela et al., 2017; Deshpande et al., 2017; François-Sévigny et al., 2022; Ng et al., 2017). Once diagnosed, people with ADHD are often treated with medication and/or counseling (Canela et al., 2017), though moderate to intense aerobic exercise has also been shown to mitigate some of the symptoms that people with ADHD may experience (Ng et al., 2017). Despite studies that “show that the long-term outcomes of ADHD treatment are better than if ADHD symptoms are left untreated” (Deshpande et al., 2017, p. 316), and that “untreated adult ADHD is associated with far-reaching adverse psychosocial and economic implications, and optimal treatment can have positive influences on patients, their families, and society” (Deshpande et al., 2017, p. 320), females are less likely than males to receive an ADHD diagnosis. Women with ADHD are often left to manage symptoms on their own, which “likely contributes to negative emotions,” (Huynh et al., 2024, 100977), some of which may stem from the societal expectations placed on women (Sander-Williams, 2024). Motherhood may pose additional challenges for women with ADHD (Holthe & Langvik, 2017). People with ADHD, especially girls, learn how to mask their symptoms (Holthe & Langvik, 2017), and some people with ADHD develop coping strategies. Some of the strategies that people with ADHD were found to use include structuring their time, being physically active, reducing stimuli and/or seeking out particular environments, avoiding commitments, being “interesting, funny or entertaining for others” (Canela et al., 2017, p. 9), and/or self-medicating (Canela et al., 2017). Additionally, ADHD may be inadvertently masked by giftedness (François-Sévigny et al., 2022). The term “gifted” often implies that “all things should come easily” (Skolnick, 2023, p. 32), and so children who are twice exceptional—once for their giftedness and once for their disability, or difference—often are not diagnosed properly. Unfortunately, little research has been done on women with ADHD or on gifted students with ADHD (François-Sévigny et al., 2022; Holthe & Langvik, 2017; Sander-Williams, 2024).

Historically, through a medical lens, ADHD is often seen as a deficit (Schippers et al., 2024). Skolnick (2023) points out that the criteria listed in the DSM-5, which professionals use to screen for ADHD, are all negative. Consequently, much of the educational research is focused on the deficits of students with ADHD. However, when using a neurodiversity lens, ADHD is not a condition to be fixed, but rather a brain type to understand. Like other brain types, there are strengths associated with the ADHD brain (Lambert, 2024). There is minimal research on the strengths of people with ADHD, but strengths that are often self-reported by people with ADHD include “creativity, high energy, hyperfocus, social skills, and courage” (Schippers et al., 2024, para. 4 Intro). In a large-scale study, researchers

showed small to moderate positive correlations between ADHD traits and sensory processing sensitivity, hyperfocus, and cognitive flexibility (Schippers et al., 2024). In a smaller, qualitative study “several participants saw themselves as being good at manipulating others or sensing the feelings and wishes of others” (Canela et al., 2017, p. 12).

As educators, supporting students with ADHD, including those who are twice exceptional, is similar to supporting other marginalized students within the mathematics classroom and requires taking into account students’ strengths as well as their difficulties (Lambert, 2024). “Best practices for 2e children are best practices for all children” (Skolnick, 2023, p. 6). Though community and school culture are influences, individual teachers have the greatest potential to create spaces where students thrive and to implement practices that allow students to enact their potential. Cawley & Wilson (2023) recognized how students often attribute their mathematical experience, positive or negative, to their teacher. They hypothesized how teachers could create more positive mathematical experiences for their students with mathematical microaffirmations. Matthews et al. (2021) also recognized the importance of the teacher in fostering a sense of belonging for mathematics students and created an observational tool based on their framework of Belonging-Centered Instruction. The framework focuses on actions teachers can take to curate interpersonal interactions with their students and the instructional techniques that support students’ sense of belonging. To be sure, teachers who establish a sense of belonging for all students “open up the classroom” (Lambert, 2024, p. 14) and provide opportunities for students who might otherwise be marginalized in a mathematics classroom setting based on their race, gender, or disability status (Reinholz, 2023). A sense of belonging is an important aspect for student persistence in STEM fields (Hedge, 2024; Reinholz, 2023).

Though many articles and books exist that are written for teachers who have students with ADHD, I was not able to find many references in the academic literature that mentioned teachers who had ADHD themselves. Swick-Jemison (2023), a woman who received an ADHD diagnosis in her forties, shared her autoethnography about finding her work as a teaching librarian at a large research university. She noted both the struggles and benefits of having ADHD in her line of work. Dolan (2021), a researcher with ADHD, documented the experience of professors with invisible disabilities and found a reluctance of participants to reveal their disabilities for fear of being labeled as academically incompetent and possibly losing their jobs. Only two of the sixteen participants in her study had revealed their disability to their employers. Relative to mathematicians with disabilities, Lambert (2024) noted: “...it is not about being either good or bad at math but about being strong in some ways, challenged in others, and learning to adapt accordingly” (Lambert, 2024, p. 39). A quick search of the internet revealed a list of blog posts and websites with tips and tricks for teachers with ADHD, but it is apparent that understanding what it means to be a mathematics educator with ADHD, or some other neurodivergent profile, is an area that may benefit from additional research. I hope that I may contribute to this gap in the literature by sharing my autoethnography.

Methodology

The methodology I used for this autoethnography was a combination of several resources and consisted of a dynamic process, which, as others who have engaged in ethnographic research know, was neither linear nor sequential (Chang, 2008). For the portions of my autoethnography that I wrote while I was in my PhD program, I was guided by the assignments provided by my professor, Dr. Jesse Bazzul, which were largely influenced by Denzin (2013). Though I do not have a copy of the assignments, I remember we were asked to complete a regression by considering our earliest memories of our formal education. We were then asked to complete a progression, in which we projected about the type of educator we wanted to be, and then, finally, we wrote an analysis of our regression and progression to uncover the important themes they revealed, also relating to education. At each stage, we engaged in a process of peer feedback, a “cognitive activity of compare and contrast [that] engenders self-examination and self-learning” (Chang, 2008, p. 41), that influenced my work. At the end of the process, I received feedback from Dr. Bazzul, who suggested ways that I might refine it, which I have also attempted to incorporate.

After re-reading that original work several years later in preparation for this project, I cried. It was emotionally draining. I shared what I had written with my new mentor, Coach Whipple, and we talked about how to proceed. I felt like much of what I had written was still relevant, but several years had passed, and I thought I should add something to it. I was not completely sure what that something was. Coach Whipple suggested I reference Chang (2008), as it had been useful to him when he constructed his autoethnography (Whipple, 2023). He mentioned that he had especially relied on photographs to stimulate his memory. So, I spent time going through my memento box, taking pictures of the artifacts inside, and uploading the photos into a PowerPoint presentation that I consulted for inspiration.

I wanted to include new material, based on the nearly ten years that had passed, and to expand my focus beyond my original charge of concentrating on my formal education. Some of the writing I did was based on suggestions made by Coach Whipple of what he perceived as important to my story. Some of the writing I did was based on the stuff in my head that needed to come out. As I continued to write, I refined my focus (Chang, 2008). Some of the additional writing made it into my autoethnography, though much of it did not. As part of refining my focus and through my discussions with Coach Whipple, I realized that my unusual career path was an important part of my story, so I constructed a timeline that traced my job history and used it as a reference.

For a long time, I had trouble making headway into either of the books, Denzin (2013) or Chang (2008), beyond what I had already read in my class, even though I carried them around with me for several months. Being perpetually short on sleep, sitting still long enough to read about methodology was a hard sell to my fatigued brain.⁴ At some point, I needed the space in my backpack, and Denzin (2013) and both of my copies of Chang (2008) ended up in a pile on my desk at home. In somewhat typical fashion, that was where they were on the day that I was in my office, determined to complete a rough draft, and could have used them. Instead, I consulted the internet for resources and found a recording of a webinar by

⁴ “Ye work too hard, my girl...I can certainly see ye don’t get enough sleep...Ye ken that ye must have sleep; ye canna think properly without some time to rest” (Pratchett, 2011, pp. 936-937).

Dr. Christopher Poulos in 2021, introducing and discussing his book *Essentials of Autoethnography* (2021). I watched it at double speed, found it promising, and purchased his book. It was just what I needed to jumpstart my efforts.

To summarize, the data I relied on is a combination of the guided writing I did as a PhD student, the artifacts I gathered and organized from my memento box, the timeline I created of my career path, and the more recent writing I did as an autoethnographer who “digs through, sifts, sorts, and mines the meanings of memories as they rise into consciousness or emerge in story or dialogue” (Poulos, 2021, p. 28). I reflected on the data I gathered and thought of it as a puzzle to put together. I worked to organize it in a way that I thought helped the themes emerge and revealed my cultural assumptions (Chang, 2008) as they relate to my profession as a mathematics educator. I chose to focus mainly on my undiagnosed ADHD because I thought that, of all the themes I could have selected, it was the one that would provide the most valuable contribution to the literature in mathematics education.

My goal was to create a work based in my truth using a descriptive style that reads like a work of fiction because “a story gets things done” (Pratchett, 2005, p. 467). I understand, however, that I am performing both roles, storyteller and researcher, and that it is not enough to simply tell my story (Chang, 2008; Poulos, 2021). Therefore, using conventions of the autoethnographic method presented within Denzin (2013), I performed a careful analysis of the stories I collected. In doing so, I attempted to engage in self-discovery while also identifying the broader cultural understandings (Chang, 2008). I hope it is a story that is about more than just me and, perhaps, provides a glimpse “into a deeper understanding of our shared human condition (Poulos, 2021, p. 57).

My Mom’s Pre-school

The Classroom

There’s a big wooden indoor climbing toy that just got put in my mom’s room. It’s awesome! I climb to the top of it, raise my arms and call out for everyone to look at me. I love this place. My mom’s room is the biggest room in the whole school, and it’s full of stuff to play with. Sometimes when it’s time to go outside for recess, I stay inside with Joseph to play. Joseph is in a wheelchair usually, but he also has a board that they strap him to so he can kind of stand up. I ask him questions while we’re playing about why he can’t move very much, but he doesn’t like to answer them. He can use his arms to play, though, and I have fun with him at the tabletop sandbox.

House Visits

Sometimes my mom makes house visits. Some of the kids have fun playrooms and toys, and I like to go with my mom. We’re doing one today, but this time I don’t like it. There’s stuff everywhere, and it smells. I had to ask my mom if I could play outside, and I’m relieved she said yes. I think I said a couple of things I shouldn’t have. I ran outside all the way to the end of the driveway; my mom told me I had to stay in the yard. I feel so much better out here. I can breathe again. The little girl who lives at the house comes out to play, too, but I don’t want to play with her. She smells a little and looks a little dirty, and she’s kind of fat. She seems to really want to play with me, but I tell her that I just want to play by

myself. She stays anyway. It takes forever for my mom to be done. We finally leave and I feel a little bad about the whole thing, but my mom says it's okay.

At My Own School

Mrs. K.

My teacher just told Jason and me that we have to go down to the office to see Mrs. K. I don't usually get in trouble, but Jason does sometimes, so I'm a little nervous on the walk down. When we get to the office, the woman who counts all the lunch money in the morning shows us where to sit. I've walked by the office enough times to know that these are the chairs where kids in trouble have to wait. After a while, Mrs. K. calls us in and shows us our spelling tests from last Friday. She says she was looking at them because it's her job to decide who gets the best handwriting award in each grade. She tells us that she was appalled when she saw our tests. Apparently, in addition to choosing who has the best handwriting, it's her job to make sure that kids don't doodle on the top of their papers. "Completely unacceptable!" she exclaims as she shakes the stack of papers. She adds, "I'm terribly disappointed in the two of you." I fight back tears as I am asked to promise not to do it anymore.⁵ I feel like it's Jason's fault. "A witch takes responsibility! Have you learned nothing, child?" (Pratchett, 2007, p. 631). I usually do a few stars and spirals at the top of my page while I'm waiting for the next word, and I've never gotten in trouble before. My teacher even told me once how much she likes my drawings; they make her smile. Jason saw me doing them during the last spelling test, and he thought it was funny. So, he drew some, too—little army guys and tanks and bullets—and by the end of the test we had both filled up the entire top of the page. I got all the words right and my handwriting was really neat, but I won't be winning the award this year.

Around the World

We're playing *Around the World* today to practice our times tables. Miss P. picks someone to start and then they stand up next to another kid. Miss P. flashes a card and the first one to shout out the answer wins and the kid who doesn't get it has to sit back down. It's called *Around the World* because the goal is to try to challenge and beat every kid all the way around the room and get back to the seat where you started. I like to play—kind of. I'm good at it and I usually win a lot of rounds. I bounce up and down and shake my hands and then point at the card as I yell out the answer. I've made it all the way around a few times before, but my face always gets hot when I play and it always takes me time to calm down again when I sit down. Plus, the other kids always rub it in if I lose.

Back at Mom's School

Sometimes, my friend Katy and I take the bus to my mom's school after we finish our own school day so that she can drive us to swim practice. We always help my mom when she asks, but mostly we watch. She is good at what she does. Her kindergarten students wait patiently in line to wash their hands at the sink, throw their paper towels in the bin, and find

⁵ It wasn't *your* fault, the Queen understood, because you were a nice person. It was just such a terrible thing that all these bad influences had made you make the wrong choices. If only you'd admit that, Tiffany, then the world would be a much happier place. (Pratchett, 2003, p. 190)

their seats. Some skip a little as they go, some giggle while they wait in line, some get reminders from my mom to keep their hands to themselves. Katy and I watch as one kid passes out the napkins, another kid comes around with the snack, and two kids help with the milk tray. They all know what to do. My mom makes a big deal about it in the morning when the kids are sitting on the rug. She always runs through what day and month it is, how many days there are in the month, how many days there are until the end of the month—let's count!—and what the weather is like. She checks in with the students charged with dressing the felt boy and girl—who always start out the day in their underwear but have a vast wardrobe for any type of weather—and then they fill in the jobs board. My mom takes the name from the top of the pile and puts it in the pocket under the first job. Anthony has napkins. The next name goes in the next slot. Crystal is doing straws today. Everyone gets a turn. Everyone contributes.

Going to Work with My Dad

I get to see what my mom does all the time, but I've never seen what my dad does. I've always been curious about what his job is like. I see him work at home—correcting papers or planning for classes—but I really want to know what his day is like. I want to see his office and classes and students. He's a professor at a college, but it's an hour away from where we live, so I've only ever been to the campus a couple of times. Today, though, I'm going to work with my dad. I'm not feeling very well; at least, I don't feel like going to school, and my mom has already used up her sick days for the year staying home with me. She wasn't going to let me stay home today but then I suggested that I go to work with Dad, and he said okay! I'm really excited for the day, even though I actually don't feel that good.

The drive is so long. We stop at Dunkin' Donuts on the way and my dad gets "the usual" and I get a chocolate doughnut. I'm excited when we finally get to campus and my dad takes me to his office. I poke around and ask questions. He shows me the pictures he has of me on his desk. He says he has to get some work done before his class today, so he gives me some paper and pens to draw. He sits at his desk while I sit on the floor. Every once in awhile, someone pops their head in to say hello, and we see a couple more people on our way to the copy room. My dad pats me on the head as they go by. In the copy room, he shows me how to make copies and how to tape over parts of the original with white paper if you didn't want certain parts of the page to show up on your copies. We walk back from the copy room to spend more time in his office. It is so quiet and boring here that I wish I had just gone to school. I keep asking my dad how much longer before his class starts. It seems like it's taking forever.

My eyes light up when he finally says it's time. My dad always tells stories about his classes and his students; I've imagined what they must be like, but I am looking forward to getting to see it all for myself. This is going to make the whole boring morning worth it; I'm finally going to see my dad teach!

I watch as my dad gathers up everything he needs for class, including the copies we made earlier, and puts everything in his briefcase. He tells me the classroom is on a different floor in the building, so he locks his office door. We walk down the stairs and through a hallway of classrooms until we get to the one where he teaches. He shows me the room,

and then he takes me a little further down the hall to show me where I should wait during his class. He gives me some quarters for the snack machine. He doesn't think it's a good idea for me to be in the class. "They had argued of course. But Mistress Weatherwax had come up with a deeply unfair one. It was: *You're eleven*. Just like that" (Pratchett, 2005, p. 475).

Getting into the Family Business

I've been out of the Navy for six years. The last two of those, I've spent working on my master's degree in sound recording technology. I took out loans to live on campus and pay for my tuition and fees. What I really want to do next is to head to Nashville and intern in a recording studio; I've picked out a few that look cool. I can't really think about how to make it work, though. I've racked up some significant student loans, and interning won't pay anything. Plus, it's a little hard to justify. I'm in my mid-30s and have just spent the last six years "fooling around"—at least compared to what I had been doing back when I was a Naval officer. I might be braver about heading to Nashville in different economic times, but the stock market just tanked, the American economy is in recession, and the job market looks grim. "'Learnin' how not to do things is as hard as learning *how* to do them. Harder, maybe. There'd be a sight more frogs in this world if I didn't know how *not* to turn people into them'" (Pratchett, 2005, p. 462).

My dad thinks I should get a job teaching math. He says I'm smart enough to pass the MTEs, I know enough math, and schools are always looking for math teachers. I follow my dad's advice and apply for my preliminary license. I could teach for a few years, save up some money, and put together my own recording studio. It's the responsible way to go, but I have to squelch the inner voice that is telling me differently.

That was the thing about thoughts. They thought themselves, and then dropped into your head in the hope that you would think so too. You had to slap them down, thoughts like that; they would take a witch over if she let them." (Pratchett, 2011, p. 942)

First-year Shock

Teaching high school is hard. Harder than anything I ever did in the Navy—and I had left there with scars and commendations. I no longer benefit from the automatic respect that the bars on my uniform afforded me, and my students don't really know anything about me.⁶ Even though it is frustrating, I want to be good at teaching, so I work hard at it. One of my colleagues tells me that I'm the only one she knows who didn't break out in tears in the middle of class at least once during my first year of teaching. She means it as a compliment—that I had made the transition and handled the pressure of being a new teacher well. I recognize, though, having been a former naval officer with leadership training and experience, that I'm not given the time or resources I need to do my job well. I don't feel my time is valued. I'm given an hour a day to prepare for 4-5 hours of teaching. Instead of providing additional time that I might use to plan for classes or provide feedback on

⁶ I took the hiver through the Dark Door, Tiffany thought as she viciously scraped food scraps into the garden for the birds. The White Horse came out of the hill for me. I got my brother and Roland back from the Queen of Elves. And I danced with the Wintersmith...I was *acceptable*. (Pratchett, 2007, pp. 681-682)

students' assignments, I'm asked to monitor students while they eat lunch. As I wait by the copier for the packets I need for class, I wonder if the town's taxpayers realize how much they are paying for someone to operate a copy machine. My dad, a specialist in educational psychology who helps prepare teachers for the rigors of the classroom, tells me good teachers learn how to take shortcuts. "Ask the teachers who have been there a few years what they do to make things easier." He also counsels, "You might want to get your doctorate."

Job Satisfaction

My mom's stress level has always been higher than my dad's when it comes to work. My dad occasionally has days where he has to get stuff done and he brings work home sometimes, but he doesn't seem to struggle to find time to do his work. Other than the long drive and the number of exams he has to grade at the end of the semester, I'm not sure I've ever heard him complain about work. He has students sometimes that can be difficult to counsel and stories about colleagues that don't get along well, and he would rather not have to attend so many meetings, but he appears to like his job overall and his stress levels are low. "I can do this forever!" he proclaims. He's certain that the key to a good life is having a job that you love.

My mom doesn't ever bring work home, but by the end of the day, she is tired. They give her too many students, some with special needs, and not enough assistance. She does her job well, but it is hard. Around the end of August each year she starts having anxiety dreams—panicked in the middle of the night that she's lost one of the kids or left school before putting everyone on the bus. She longs for the time when she doesn't have to go back in September. She's said it to me more than once; she only had two career choices as a woman and she chose teaching over nursing. She is pursuing her certification in instructional technology. What she really wants to do is help teachers plan lessons that incorporate technology. She could use a break from her classroom.

I can feel my own tension rising as August draws to a close. I don't have the anxiety dreams like my mom did, but it's hard knowing that the summer's almost over and another school year will be starting soon. Having taught high school for seven years now, I have a different perspective on what it means to be a teacher. Teaching is a commitment. Great teachers put in such a tremendous amount of time and effort. Even lousy teachers work hard. I realize why my mom came home tired every day (she was one of the great ones), and it makes me so proud to reflect on my mom's accomplishments and her commitment to teaching. I never appreciated how hard her job was when I was growing up. And she went every day even though it was hard, and she made a lot of difference in a lot of kids' lives. "*That* is the root and heart and soul and center of witchcraft, that is. The soul and center!" (Pratchett, 2005, p. 461). I wish I could turn back the clock for my mom and bring her to the place where she could choose to be anything she wanted. It makes me grateful to be part of a generation where women have choice, but I wish that I could be in a place where I wanted to be like my mom. Instead, I'm choosing to be like my dad.

Realizations

Family Support

Of course I was a good student! My parents were both educators, and with my mom teaching preschool before she switched to kindergarten, I started school not long after I was born. I knew just what was expected of me and how to act in school. I was respectful of my teachers and classmates, involved in our lessons, and worked hard on my assignments. I got lots of positive feedback from my teachers, and I heard them tell my parents what a joy it was to have me in class. My parents had done everything to set me up for success in school. When I was a kid, they read to me, talked with me, sang with me, and laughed with me. They made sure I got enough sleep, fed me nutritious food, encouraged me to play, and valued my creativity. They provided time for me to interact with other people, took me on trips, and let me pursue lots of different activities. They expected me to complete chores, help around the house, and keep my room clean, though it never really was. They were involved in my activities, volunteering as scout leaders and coaches, and driving us to practices, and they were always in the audience for concerts and shows.

Even my older brothers helped set me up for success in school. I knew all of my teachers before I had them and just about every project that I was going to complete along the way from kindergarten through high school. Knowing what good kids my brothers had been, teachers rejoiced when they saw my unusual last name on their rosters.

My family helped structure my life to be able to do my best, but I was in on it, too. I worked hard and was motivated to do well. I recognized the value of hard work, but I guess I didn't realize that not everyone had such a strong support system. At least I didn't think about it too much. I knew that not everyone's family was just like mine, but I think I chalked up most of the differences to personal choices. My parents worked hard and made smart, responsible decisions. We were a "good" family.

Making Assumptions

I've been teaching about three years, and I've started to realize I've made too many assumptions about students and have been too judgmental. There might be reasons for my students' "poor choices" and unwillingness to try harder. Another year and it's hitting me hard. I've been reading about the purposes of schooling and realizing that the system I thrived in makes it worse for some kids. Lots of kids get filtered—lots of times for not very good reasons. Everyone in the system is trying hard, but the system isn't flexible. I want to be flexible. I want to connect with students and figure out how to help them in ways that they need. I want to make math more accessible so that all students can understand it and pursue it and not be filtered. But it's hard, and I'm always struggling for time: "...whatever she did, it wasn't quite enough. She got up earlier every day and went to bed later, but it still wasn't enough" (Pratchett, 2015, pp. 1335–1336). I know what I'm supposed to do, or at least I have an idea, but I don't feel like I have the time to prepare the way I'd like. I don't have enough time to give students the right feedback.

Filtered Spouse

Thomas, my spouse, didn't do so well in school. They didn't know it back then, but as an adult he was diagnosed with severe ADHD and mild dyslexia. Additionally, he stutters. He

says he grew up thinking he was a “fat, dumb shit,” yet he’s one of the most creative people I know. In college, he was studying to be a high school shop teacher and he would have been a great one; he really knows how to relate to kids. But his college advisor told him to forget about it—with his speech issues, he’d never be able to teach. So, after three years of college, he transferred to a different school and started again as a first-year student. He didn’t graduate.

Other Opportunities?

I’ve been keeping my eyes open for jobs at the college level. It’s what I originally thought I’d like to do, at least since I started teaching high school. I’ve gotten used to my job at the high school now, though. I don’t feel like I did when I first started teaching and couldn’t wait to leave. I know how to do my job well now, and I think I might be making a difference. I feel like I’m an especially good role model for the girls in my classes. But, there are still so many things that aren’t right. I’d like something with more flexibility and autonomy. A place where I don’t have to sign a slip of paper when a kid wants to use the bathroom.

Most colleges are looking for someone with a PhD, though, and I don’t have mine yet. Occasionally, a job comes up that says, “PhD preferred” and I apply to those. I figure at the very least it will be good practice for when I finally have my PhD. In the Spring of 2015, a job came up at a school in Vermont. The school only had 500 students, and it specialized in working with students who had learning differences. I remember hearing an advertisement for it once a few years back. A kid came on the radio and said how he had struggled with ADHD and how Landmark had made such a difference in his life. At the time I heard it, I remember thinking how hard it must be for those teachers dealing with whole classes full of ADHD students! That was before I met Thomas. Now, I’m intrigued by it. I want to know what Landmark is doing to help their students. I want to be part of a team that appreciates people with learning differences. Landmark is welcoming students with differences and figuring out how to arrange their system to support them. I feel guilty leaving my high school, but I’m excited for something new, I’m excited to learn how an educational system can be more inclusive, and I’m excited to learn some strategies that might be helpful for Thomas. “‘Well,’ said Tiffany, ‘she will probably feel what we call a little *glow*, because she has helped someone who needed help’” (Pratchett, 2015, pp. 1461–1462).

My People?

It’s winter convocation, and the featured speaker is a science professor whose office is down the hall from mine in the brand-new STEM building. We are friendly. She is kind, a little quirky, and very passionate about what she does. This is her 20th year at Landmark. She raises both hands up and exclaims, “I have found my people!” as she recounts the day when she first arrived on campus. An applause breaks out in the auditorium as I think back to my own first day on campus. I also celebrated. Being a professor is so much saner than teaching high school, even with the long drives I make back and forth each week and with the substantial pay cut I took. There’s an aura of wellness that pervades the Landmark campus,

and I have been soaking it all in, along with all the professional development that is constantly being offered. I have my own office and most of my classes are going well. I had to ask for help with the kid who kept standing up and pacing in my statistics class, though. With his grunts and arm-flaps, I could tell he was frustrated, but I couldn't ever get him to tell me what was wrong. I'm very happy to be here, but I'm not sure these are my people, I conclude, as I return my focus back to Kim's speech.

Learning Differences

I'm starting to feel more comfortable now that I've been at Landmark for a couple of semesters. I like all of the different personalities that I have in my classes, and I like figuring out how to design lessons that are accessible to them. It's a challenge, and I think I have room to improve. I've been thinking about what is and what isn't important about what I teach. And I've been thinking a lot about what a disability is. Or, is it just a difference? "Change the story, change the world" (Pratchett, 2005, p. 531). I appreciate my small class sizes, and feel like I've been able to get to know most of my students pretty well. I've worked hard to try and make myself accessible to my students. I think there are lessons that I could learn here that might translate well to the public school system. I would like to try to communicate those lessons someday and to help translate them into the public schools so that we might create an educational system that can accommodate more, or even all, students.

Play Groups

New Moms

I show up at the new moms' group at the library. I'm excited to be a mom and want to make sure I do everything right. I figure all the moms must be feeling tired and emotional like me.

"Oh, wow! She's so alert!" one of the moms exclaims as she looks at my baby's wide-open eyes. I smile as another mom agrees.

"Is she always like that?" a third mom asks, adding, "All my baby does is sleep!" They all laugh at their shared experience. I am both proud and jealous. My baby is so obviously intelligent, but I could use some sleep.

Birthday Party

My baby is nine months old already, and we are at a party for a little girl who is turning one. I know lots of the moms and their kids from all the playgroups we attend. My daughter needs her diaper changed, so I head for the back room. There are some other moms already in there doing the same thing. I watch discreetly as one of them changes her baby on the bed. We did prenatal yoga together before our kids were born, only a week or so apart, so we are friendly. I'm amazed at how easy she makes diaper changing look, and I'm struck by how patient her baby is. She finishes the job quickly, and picks up her baby with a few smiles and words of encouragement. She moves from the side of the bed, revealing a nightstand behind her with a small lamp on top. It's the only source of light in the otherwise dim room. My daughter, still in my arms, points to it and says, emphatically, "'ight." I smile

and respond, “Yes, Baby Girl, that’s a light.” I see the other mom’s eyes get wide. I don’t think her baby speaks yet.

“Wow, she’s verbal, huh?”

“Yes,” I reply, a proud mama. “Light is one of her favorite words.” I smile like it’s no big deal as I try to make sure I have everything I need within an arm’s length on the floor so I can change my daughter’s diaper. I don’t dare try changing her on the bed. She cries and squirms as I work to clean up the mess and get a new diaper on. I’m glad all the other moms have already gone back to the party.

Doctor Visits

All three of us go to our daughter’s 2-year-old well visit. Thomas and I have learned that it takes both of us to manage. We take turns following her around the waiting room, making sure she stays within the boundaries and plays with the toys appropriately. I’m glad when our name is finally called. Our daughter is happy to follow the friendly nurse into the back. The nurse smiles and talks in a baby voice, entertaining my daughter, as she explains everything she’s doing. After she finishes measuring our daughter, the nurse shows the three of us to a room to wait for the doctor. I know this will be the hardest part. Our daughter explores the examination room as my husband and I try to keep her from destroying it. She rips the strip of paper on the examining table and tries to grab at the box full of ear probe covers hanging on the wall. Thomas takes one of the plastic gloves and blows it up to try to distract her. I pick her up several times to see if she’ll settle, but she keeps on squirming down, anxious to explore. Finally, the doctor comes and immediately comments on her energy level. He does a thorough exam, standing in between Thomas and me as we guard the edges of the table, and declares that she is a healthy kid. He wants to spend some time talking with us, though. We both try to listen, but only one of us can as the other monitors our daughter. The doctor mentions that much of what our daughter is doing is attention-seeking and starts to recommend some parenting strategies. I don’t hear what he says, though, because our daughter is headed for the door. I move to grab her, but the doctor turns his body and blocks my way. He is a tall man, and I think he’s used to kids listening to him. He tells our daughter, “No!” but she turns the knob and opens the door anyway. The doctor is too slow to react, and I can’t get around him, so I watch it all unfold. “‘Why’re we stopping? Why’re we stopping here? We’ve got to catch her!’” (Pratchett, 2003, p. 87). The doctor heads out into the hallway, announcing to his staff, “We’ve got a runner!” as my daughter makes her way around the other patients and nurses in the hall. After some commotion, our daughter is herded back into the exam room. I am laughing and mortified all at the same time. I would have had her if the doctor hadn’t gotten in the way! The doctor suggests we start seeing the behavioral therapist.

Being a Campus Leader

The campus is working to diversify its student population, and I participate in all the grant-funded and cross-campus professional development opportunities that are offered. I was asked to coordinate the last one, and then doing a good job with that led to another offer

to lead our campus assessment efforts. I've tried to become a bit of a campus leader, at least when it comes to inclusive teaching practices.

"Witches don't have leaders! You've just said that, Nanny!"

"Yes," said Nanny. "And you must be the best damn leader that we don't have."
(Pratchett, 2011, p. 1318)

Last fall, I helped our campus host a fall conference for NE-COMMIT, an organization that I've been a part of for a few years now that supports teachers and professors interested in inquiry-based learning and active learning. It's my favorite group—small enough to know everyone, large enough to keep the fresh ideas flowing. It's all very grass-rootsy and organic. We were able to get a great guest speaker because I figured out how to coordinate some funding for professional development workshops on campus the day before the conference. It was a lot of work in addition to the classes I was teaching, the tutoring I was doing in the Academic Resource Center, and all the Assessment Committee work I was doing. I have no idea why I scheduled our Assessment Committee meeting for that week; I'm pretty sure I still have to type up the notes for the meeting.

My People

At the start of their session on how to make mathematics classrooms more accessible and equitable for students with disabilities, the keynote speaker at the NE-COMMIT conference shares that they have invisible disabilities. Modeling disability justice, they take a moment to convey to the conference attendees that it is not necessary to mask⁷ during the session. We are urged to take care of ourselves and to be our authentic selves. It is clear as the session progresses and attendees begin to open up, that there is a contingent of neurodivergent people in the room. I stand up to help someone who has come late to the session find a seat. Thinking there might be other latecomers, I decide to stay in the back of the room. I like it back here. I can see everyone, and it feels good to move. I sway back and forth, glad not to be concerned that I'm taking up too much desk space or being too fidgety for the person next to me. I am attentive and comfortable. I soak it all in as I participate, and, as I look around the room, I realize that I have found my people.

At Home

My husband has a huge heart, a willingness to help anyone in need, and an ability and desire to talk with everyone (he doesn't ever talk "to" anyone). He knows how to motivate groups of people to get things done, and he has a creative soul and an artful eye. He struggles with executive functioning, though, and, even though work is going well for me, by the time I get home, I'm exhausted. We struggle to keep up with our home. Our kid is a colorful combination of both of our souls—intelligent, friendly, kind, funny, curious, athletic, artistic, and ready to take charge! Her energy level is off-the-charts high, she experiences intense emotions, and her room looks just like mine did when I was a kid. I see myself in her, and sometimes I feel like I've been sent back in time to watch myself grow up.

⁷ "Boffo, yes. A good name for it. Boffo, indeed. The art of expectations. Show people what they want to see, show'em what they think should be there. I have a reputation to keep up, after all" (Pratchett, 2007, p. 638).

I don't want to stifle her spirit. It's hard to find the right balance at home, though. Home was always where I re-energized, but now it seems to wear me out even more. I seek out some counseling because I feel like I could use some help. "‘Cackling’ to a witch, didn't just mean nasty laughter. It meant your mind drifting away from its anchor. It meant you losing your grip" (Pratchett, 2007, p. 592). There are lots of things I want to talk about with my therapist, but one of them is that I think I've realized that I have ADHD. My therapist doesn't think it matters; an ADHD diagnosis is something that they make when a kid is having trouble in school, and I have a PhD.

Conversations with My Daughter

Superhero? (4 years old)

"Mom, can you come with me to the bedroom?" my daughter asks. I haven't been sitting very long.

"No, not right now, Kid. I'm still eating supper."

"But I'm scared to go all by myself," she explains. I look down the hall; I really don't want to get up.

"The bedroom light is on already," I tell her as I tell myself that this is something she can do on her own.

She points to the hallway. "But, those lights aren't!"

"Well, why don't you just use your superhero vision for that part?" I encourage. "Go really fast...you can make it!" I laugh at myself, but she doesn't join me. I feel her hand on my arm as she gently rubs it up and down. She keeps her hand there as she looks into my eyes and breaks the news to me gently. "Mom, I have to tell you something. I'm not *actually* a superhero. I just *pretend* to be one sometimes." She emphasizes the words to make sure I understand, then pauses for a moment to stroke my arm again and let me process her words. When she thinks I'm ready, she looks back up and asks gently, "So, can you please come with me?"

Cupcakes (4.5 years old)

"Oh no, the little cupcake fell off!" she tells me. I am glad she is not upset.

"Oh no!" I echo. "I hope it didn't land on the frosting!"

"Mom, they always land on the frosting. It's a rule," she states, matter-of-factly.

"Really?" I ask, wanting to know more.

"Yeah. It's like the butter on the bread rule—they're cousins," she explains.

I laugh and ask, "Where'd you learn about that?"

"It's just how it works, Mom."

Mac 'n' Cheese (5.5 years old)

"Mom, did you know the top of the pot is the bottom of the bowl?" my daughter asks casually as she takes a bite of her mac 'n' cheese. I take a moment to ponder her question.

"Yes," I say, "that's very insightful," as I smile over at my mom who has joined us for an afternoon out. I add, "That would make a good saying on a fortune cookie!"

My daughter looks at me and inquires, "Do you get it, Mom?"

I nod. "Yes, I understand what you are saying. It's very clever. What about you, Nana?" I

ask my mom, my eyes twinkling. “Do you get it?” My mom nods and replies affirmatively, but for some reason, despite our assurances, my daughter is not convinced that we completely understand. She begins her explanation, motioning in the air to show us how a scoop from the top of the pot would end up in the bottom of the bowl. We wait patiently for her to finish. Smiling, I say, “Thanks for the clarification, Kid. Now we *really* get it!” My mom laughs; there’s something familiar to her about the whole exchange.

Papa (almost 6 years old)

“Hey, Mom...Papa is really old, right?”

“Yes, he is really old. Just like people come in all different sizes, shapes, and colors, they also come in all different ages.” I am glad for the opportunity to talk about diversity.

“Well, who do you know that was born when they were four?” I have piqued her curiosity.

“What?” I ask. I’m not sure I heard her right.

She repeats the question: “Who do you know that was born when they were four?”

Still confused, I answer, “Umm...no one?”

“Mom! Then why did you say that people come in all different ages?”

“Oh, okay,” I say, understanding now. “They don’t actually *come* in all different ages. Everyone is born as a baby, but on this Earth right now there are people of all different ages.”

“Oh, okay, Mom. Then why did you say that they come in all different ages? That was confusing!”

I smile. “I guess I should have been more clear with my word choice,” I concede. I am impressed with her logic.

Undiagnosed ADHD

I’m missing my mom now. I still see her, but it’s not like before. My dad and I have locked horns so my daughter still goes over to my parents’ house, but I don’t.⁸ I’m spending more time at my own home, and it’s not easy here. Thomas bears the brunt of the stigma from my concerned family and from our entitled neighbors. I try to be understanding about it all, but it takes a lot of patience and I am frustrated. It was easier when I could escape to my parents’ house. Now, I feel like I’m always in crisis mode, even when I’m trying to do routine things. Getting a precocious 5-year-old to hurry up and make the bus is hard, especially when none of the things you need are where you left them, and she has no interest in hurrying. I can feel my mental health tanking. And it hits me like a ton of bricks. It is my epiphany. “Nothing’s louder than the end of a song that’s always been there” (Pratchett, 2003, p. 57). All the structure, all the exercise, all the guidance, all the shared meals, all the opportunities to talk and share. Sure, I had a messy room, I forgot things a lot, I struggled with time-blindness, and I was sensitive to noise. Yes, I was surprised when I

⁸ “I’m frightened for her. Frightened to mah boots.”

“Why?”

“Because I’ve been watchin’ the shadows, Mr. Rob,” said Billy. “The sun is movin’. It’s slippin’ doon the sky.”

“Aye, weel, that’s whut the sun does—” Rob began.

Billy shook his head. “Nay, Mr. Rob. Ye dinna understand! I’m tellin ye that’s no’ the sun o’ the big wide world. That’s the sun o’ the soul o’ her.” (Pratchett, 2005, p. 434)

found out that not everyone had a continuous inner dialogue or such a vivid imagination. “To be a witch, you have to have a very good imagination. Just now, Tiffany was wishing that hers wasn’t *quite* so good” (Pratchett, 2005, p. 322). I understand, now, that not everyone experiences memories as scenes they can replay, even all the more clearly for awkward moments. I guess I assumed that everyone reviewed their past conversations and rehearsed their future ones. I figured everyone was swimming against the stream of negative self-talk. I knew I was good at getting things done under pressure, and I always found it easy to “read” people, even though I did not always know what to say. I appreciated that I was intelligent, creative, and funny, that I had leadership qualities, and I exuded enthusiasm, but I didn’t think it was any big deal. I didn’t recognize my strengths as unique. Until now, I never knew I had ADHD. “‘Aye, she’s got First Sight, sure enough,’ said William’s voice behind Tiffany as she stared into the world of the Queen. ‘She’s seein’ what’s *really* there....’” (Pratchett, 2003, p. 144). The reason I didn’t know until now⁹ is because all the things that you are supposed to do to support someone with ADHD were built into my life. I see, now, that my family, my teachers, my coaches, the Navy, and my friends all helped me along the way.

As an adult now, though, who no longer has the extra support that buys me the extra time I need to accomplish my work, things are hard. Thanks to my mom, I know enough to be an independent woman, but being a parent in a neurodivergent household is overwhelming. I need some help. I wish I didn’t have to figure out for myself that I had ADHD. “Even when she felt sick and dizzy, and quite interested in knowing where the privy was as soon as possible, Tiffany still had ears that worked and a mind that, however much she tried, wouldn’t stop thinking” (Pratchett, 2005, p. 318).

Analysis

Though narrative writing is often a personal experience, with the structure of the writing being chosen by the author, there are conventions that provide some definition to the genre of autoethnography (Denzin, 2013). The nine categories that Denzin (2013) identifies as being characteristic of autoethnography are:

- (1) the existence of others; (2) the influence and importance of race, gender, and class; (3) family beginnings; (4) turning points; (5) known and knowing authors and observers; (6) objective life markers; (7) real persons with real lives; (8) turning-point experiences; and (9) truthful statements distinguished from fictions. (Denzin, 2013, p. 7)

Though I could potentially address all nine categories, I have chosen to analyze the writing I have included in this autoethnography using categories 1, 2, 3, and 8. I begin with category 1.

Category 1: The Existence of Others

Looking back at my narrative, I tried to determine who my “others” were. Recognizing whom I identify as “others” may provide understanding of how I identify myself. I noticed that

⁹ “Oh, dear. It wasn’t a very difficult conclusion to reach. A tortoise with a bad leg could have jumped to it” (Pratchett, 2011, pp. 1146-1147).

the stories I shared relating to my own educational experience, starting in my mom's preschool, mostly focused on my interactions with other kids. As I moved to sharing my stories of being a teacher, the focus remained about my feelings toward my students. Though they were present, none of my stories foregrounded my teachers.

From an early age, through my mom's preschool, I was exposed to kids whom I perceived as different from me—Joseph who used a wheelchair and the little girl with whom I did not want to play. In my own school, I wrote about other students—Jason, who got me in trouble, and the kids who rubbed it in when I finally had to sit down in the *Around the World* math game. I thought of myself as a “good” kid and a smart kid, implying the existence of other students who were not.

My parents were both educators, and though I never got to see exactly what my dad did in his classroom, I knew exactly what my mom did, and, to me, their job was to help students. The stories I heard at home from both of them were often of the students who frustrated them. When I first became a teacher myself, I thought it was my job to impart my wisdom to my students, and I was annoyed by students who made my classes difficult. I was reflective, however, and interested in becoming a better teacher for my students and so I did my best to figure out how to become one.

As a high school teacher, I transitioned from someone who lectured to my students to someone who provided guided, active learning. I also modified my perspective relating to student accommodations. Based on my worldview when I first started teaching, I thought that if students were not succeeding, they just needed to try harder. In part, though, I also think I was annoyed at having to give students accommodations because it made it more difficult for me; I was struggling to keep up with the demands of teaching, and providing special accommodations for students added another layer to my preparations. As I gained some experience and learned more about the role of mathematics education, mainly from within my PhD program, I shifted my perspective from being annoyed at having to provide accommodations to trying to cultivate a space that was conducive for all students to learn.

I got more curious about learning differences after I met Thomas and during the time I spent at Landmark. However, even immersed in an environment at Landmark that celebrated difference, I still did not recognize that I was different or that I was someone who needed support. Accommodations were so “others” could succeed. It took the overwhelm of motherhood—with the extra parenting challenge of raising a twice exceptional child—while simultaneously trying to compensate for my husband's and my own challenges, for me to reach the place where I was no longer able to mask my symptoms. As Skolnick emphasizes: “Parenting is hard. Parenting a twice exceptional child is downright exhausting. It can wreak havoc on the most career accomplished, the most generous philanthropist, the most successful entrepreneur, and the most well-intentioned parents” (Skolnick, 2023, p. 97). I was 49 years old, just over five years into parenthood, when I first suspected that I had ADHD.

I think the discovery that my “others” were students reveals that I had more to learn about the perspective of students, when I myself was a student, and now that I am an educator. Through this autoethnographic experience, I have. Whereas I used to think that it was *other* students who had difficulties, I realize now that I had them, too. More

importantly, I realize that with the right support system, as I had, students with differences can succeed, perhaps without even realizing that they are “different.” My story eventually transitions into my wanting to be a mathematics educator who provides students with the opportunities and environment they need to thrive. Having revealed my own struggles, I have a better sense of community with my students. They are no longer “others”; they are my husband and my daughter, and they are me. Next, I transition to Denzin’s second category, focusing on gender.

Category 2: The Influence and Importance of Gender

All of my preschool friends were male. Even as I think now, I cannot recall any friends from preschool who were female. Though I think there were other factors involved with the little girl who wanted to play with me during the house visit, I do think part of why I did not want to play with her was because she was a girl. In terms of the observations that I made relating to the gender of my parents and their work, I find it intriguing that I had a complete awareness of what my mom did and very little about what my dad did. As a child, I implied a message of access based on gender. There was a mystery to what my dad did that I felt I was not privy to. Additionally, I sensed an imbalance in my parents’ job roles and requirements and their senses of satisfaction. Though I knew they both worked hard and were good at what they did, I was very conscious of my dad having a better work scenario than my mom.

I think, in part, my reasoning for joining the military was to show that I, and women, were tough. Moreover, reflecting back on how I felt after I got out of the Navy—where I had been accustomed to being given the respect of a man—I was shocked at the lack of respect for my time and efforts that I was making as a teacher. After I’d shared my frustrations about teaching with my parents, my dad’s counseling to get my doctorate, like much of the advice that he gave me as a child, was advice that he would give a son. Throughout my life, he communicated that as a female, I was disadvantaged, and I got the message from my dad that the things that were considered good for a woman were not good enough for me. I needed to rise above my female-ness, and he was there to help me do it. I owe much of my confusion relating to my gender to my dad, but I also owe much of the way I have navigated through the obstacles placed in front of me as a woman because of his guidance. Thinking now, though, I am really confused if they actually were obstacles. However, throughout my lifetime, I have seen progress relating to gender acceptance and I have appreciated the role of being able to relate to and be a mentor for students of all genders in my own classroom. Having addressed the role gender played in my autoethnography, I move to my third category, also Denzin’s third category, to analyze my family beginnings.

Category 3: Family Beginnings

I have always been especially close to my mom. As a preschooler, I loved being in my mom’s classroom. As a kid in school, I used to pretend I was sick so the nurse would call my mom to pick me up. Some of it was boredom, I think, but mostly, I just missed my mom. On weekends, my mom and I would go on shopping trips, and she and I would spend the day shuffling through the racks at factory outlets looking for bargains and having lunch. My brothers hardly ever came with us, and my dad never came. So, my mom and I had lots of

time to talk and share. I knew my mom wasn't completely happy with how everything had gone in her life and she instilled in me, at every opportunity, the importance of being an "independent woman." I remember telling her that I didn't think I ever wanted to get married. "'When I go around the houses,' Tiffany said quietly, 'I also see how some of the marriages, well, they're not really...'" That hung in the air" (Pratchett, 2015, p. 1408). My mom understood. Once I left for college and then went on to the Navy, my mom came to visit whenever she could, wherever I was in the world, and arranged for tickets home so I could come home when I had leave. Home was a place where I felt rejuvenated, and I have always loved spending time with my mom.

My mom always supported my interests, but it was my dad who provided career advice and suggestions for the paths I might pursue. I have valued my dad's advice and, as with his suggestions to consider teaching and then to pursue my doctorate, I have often taken it. Though it is my mom that I am closer to, my dad has been the one to provide direction.

My family beginnings have been more than just beginnings, however. Despite my ambition to be an independent woman, and with the exception of some of the recent difficulties I have had with my family of origin that relate to my own family's struggles, I have counted on their support throughout my life. Recognizing the support my family has provided me has allowed me to be more cognizant of some my turning-point experiences, which is the next, and final, Denzin category I have used to analyze my autoethnography.

Category 8: Turning-point Experiences

In my early experiences within the educational system, I speak as one who is innocently thriving. I am unconcerned with, and mostly unaware of, others who were floundering. As Skolnick (2023) stated: "having nothing but their own experience and worldview to consider, gifted and [twice exceptional] people often regard their incredible and unique abilities as typical or ordinary" (p. 28). One of the turning points I experienced as a teacher was realizing that my ability to learn quickly was a gift and that I had to learn to relate to my students who struggled with concepts that had come readily for me. After realizing this strength, I grew to be more patient, to encourage productive struggle, and to celebrate progress.

Another turning point occurred when I realized that school did not treat all kids the same. For a long time, I had not thought of school as being anything but a positive force within our society. Because my parents dedicated their time and efforts to being exceptional educators and I admired them for their contributions, I figured that the system had to be good. Then, as I realized at some point that my parents were human and flawed, I also realized that our school system, a human creation, was also flawed. Even worse, I had been complicit with this system that is biased toward particular types of students, reinforces stereotypes, and spotlights disabilities. Sometimes it even creates them (Skolnick, 2023). It was the realization that school might be doing harm to some students that gave me the feeling that Kanu & Glor (2006) refer to:

This realization has the effect of awaking one from a dream/nightmare where one gains insight into the harm caused to others, self, the immediate environment, and the world. This awaking allows possible growth to occur, but it is costly to the individual. (Kanu & Glor, 2006, p. 108)

The realizations hurt (Kanu & Glor, 2006), and though I knew that I did not want to be part of a system that filters students into particular roles or limits students' learning by imposing particular constraints, I was not clear about how to go about making changes. With the awareness, however, I became a more sympathetic instructor, who was more understanding and supportive of students' circumstances and needs.

Relatedly, a third turning point occurred when I realized how important my family had been to my own success. I learned that not all students necessarily receive the same support or have the same resources that I was privileged to have as a student in school, and continued to have as an educator. As I reflect on my teaching career, I have gone from someone who did not think anyone should get special support in a classroom, to recognizing that some students benefit from accommodations, to realizing that even though I did not have any official accommodations, I was getting all sorts of support along the way that allowed me to accomplish great things, especially academically. *"Open your eyes, and then open your eyes again"* (Pratchett, 2005, p. 308).

Discussion and Conclusions

As with any study, there are limitations to this one. Much of it relies on my memory, and "memory selects, shapes, limits, and distorts the past" (Chang, 2008, p. 72). I chose to focus only on specific portions of my life and have left out significant facets and time periods because I did not think they advanced this particular story. I attempted to complement my memory with photographs and artifacts and speak to the universality of my story, as well as provide some insight into my bustling brain, through quotes from a children's fantasy book, but I did not attempt to collect any data from anyone other than myself. Still, I think that I have successfully done the work of an autoethnographer. Though there are other stories I could have told, this is the one that the autoethnography process led me to in this moment, and I have situated it within a relevant sociocultural perspective that contributes to the literature in mathematics education.

When I first did some writing toward this project as a PhD student, my main findings were related to gender and feminism. Ten years later, those threads are still prevalent within my story, though I have removed some of the pieces that emphasize those themes. Additionally, I think other researchers have communicated those themes well. As "meanings are always in motion" (Denzin, 2013, p. 37), I think the more important realization from this work has to do with being an intelligent, capable, overwhelmed woman with undiagnosed ADHD who wants help for herself, her family, and for other neurodivergent math educators and students. I hope that I might rally researchers in mathematics education to focus on learning more about neurodiversity, especially as it relates to supporting neurodivergent students and leveraging neurodivergent educators.

Though a personal diagnosis of ADHD might have been useful at certain points in my life, overall, I feel very fortunate. I had a support system that in the absence of formal treatment, allowed me to thrive in academic and work settings. I have come to recognize my strengths in addition to my challenges, and I am grateful for the unique and rewarding experiences I have had, most likely because I was not treated for ADHD. Schippers et. al (2024) notes: "People with ADHD tend to switch jobs often and strength-based career

advice might help them find a fitting job quicker” (2024, para. 11 Discussion), but I do not regret the path I have followed. I think my journey has made me a more adept, creative, and empathetic mathematics educator. However, getting an official diagnosis, and perhaps being treated with medication, even at this late stage in my life, might be beneficial for my desire to support neurodivergent students. I think the ability to focus more readily might enable me to spend more energy and time working to help my students and less energy trying to keep up with my competing thoughts and inefficient work processes. It might help me to refine my craft and allow me to find a better balance between my work and home.

Additionally, I am grateful for the path I took that has led me to recognize my own neurodiversity. I do not think I would have ever realized I had ADHD had I not pursued a career as a mathematics educator who is interested in creating inclusive learning spaces. Learning more about myself, ADHD in general, and the term “twice exceptional” has better prepared me to support my daughter’s growth. Whether I have ADHD or not, this learning process has made me a more informed parent and educator.

Being undiagnosed, there is potential that I do not have ADHD. As Skolnick (2023) notes: “research grapples with teasing apart true ADHD symptoms and gifted characteristics that can look like ADHD symptoms” (p. 74), and there is potential that I have not assessed my own situation appropriately. Though my daughter attends a weekly counseling session to help her navigate the world, school, and our struggles at home, she has not yet received an official diagnosis of ADHD. Moreover, neither I nor my daughter have been tested for giftedness, though I highly suspect, based on reading, experience, and observation, that we would both fit the criteria. As of this writing, I am awaiting an appointment with a neurologist to try to find out more about my personal situation. However, with or without official diagnoses, I think the autoethnographic journey I have undertaken is important. I hope that it can contribute to the mathematics education community’s awareness of the need to support neurodivergent students within our learning spaces. I also think that more research and awareness are necessary for learning how to identify gifted students who also struggle—2e students—and the strategies that math teachers, and teachers in general, can use to support them. The current research is especially lacking at identifying girls who struggle with ADHD. Though my personal story is one of mostly academic successes, it would be a shame to prevent some of our world’s most creative thinkers from pursuing mathematics because we are not providing a learning environment that recognizes their needs, cultivates their interests, and appreciates their neurodiversity.

I know the work is worthwhile because when I share with others about my time at Landmark where I taught classrooms full of students who learn differently, or about the efforts I make to try to make my current classrooms more inclusive, I almost always evoke a response, from whomever I am speaking, about someone they know who had difficulty in school, and especially in math class. Difficulty in school, and with math in particular, is a universal theme within our society. Had I been born into a different family or community, I might have had a very different school experience because of my undiagnosed ADHD. My husband’s story serves as an example of someone whose support system was not as strong. He struggled through school and never completed his college program because he was specifically told, based on his stutter, that he could not be a teacher.

As a mathematics education community, we need to work to address this theme so we can figure out how to make our classrooms places where all students have the opportunity to thrive. As Reinholz (2023) states: “Overall, mathematics education research has done a much better job of recognizing what is not working, while developing concrete strategies to address inequities is still a challenge” (p. 4). As it is so salient in my own life right now, magnified by this autoethnographic process, I intend for my particular impact to be helping to create learning environments in my own classroom and across campus where neurodivergent students are able to flourish.

Additionally, I wonder whether there would be benefit to establishing a community of neurodivergent mathematics educators who could support one another. I am unaware of any organizations that specifically support neurodivergent mathematicians or mathematics educators. I am grateful to have found support and community within a regional group of mathematics educators known as NE-COMMIT. NE-COMMIT is a forward-thinking organization whose supportive structure welcomes contributions from neurotypical and neurodivergent members. It is my affiliation with NE-COMMIT that has led me down the path of completing my autoethnography. Engaging with this progressive group has provided me with the hope that we, as a mathematics education community, are making forward progress in creating spaces that recognize the benefit of contributions from all. However, I think it is a worthwhile endeavor to attempt to “mainstream” neurodivergent profiles among mathematics educators and within the professor ranks in general. As Reinholz (2023) noticed:

In recent years I have been more open about my identities. In sharing my own experiences openly, I found that my students also responded with openness. Students were willing to share aspects of their identities—especially related to disability—that they would never have shared in the decade prior. My authenticity created the foundation for more authentic relationships with students (p. 44).

Though it is often perceived as a professional risk to share disability (Dolan, 2021; Reinholz, 2023), being authentic as mathematics educators encourages our students to remove their own masks, and in turn allows for us to better serve our students. Moreover, revealing our own struggles may provide motivation for our students who also struggle to persist with mathematics. What better way to inspire a neurodivergent student to pursue their interest in mathematics than to see a reflection of themselves already contributing to the field?

“She smiled again, and it was Granny Aching’s smile. Things would be different one day” (Pratchett, 2003, p. 257).

Afterword

I attempted to make my gratitude clear within my autoethnography, but I would like to make a few additions here. I am thankful to Dr. Jesse Bazzul for introducing me to the genre of autoethnography and for recognizing the potential of my work. I am thankful to Dr. Alex Moore for responding to my inquiry with interest, for introducing me to my writing mentor, and for assuring me, even as he turned over the editor-in-chief duties, that he was going to

see my paper through to the end. I am thankful to Ms. Mary Kane, the director of our campus writing center, for reading through my paper and helping me find all the places I could polish before sending it in for publication. I am thankful to Dr. Kyle Whipple—Coach Whipple—who was so patient and encouraging throughout this project. He kept me moving in the right direction and invested far more time with me than he initially signed up for. Without his guidance, it is doubtful I would have ever finished, and, if I had, it would not have been as good. He is a coach to the core and coached me to do my best work from start to finish. I'm also grateful to have become friends in the process of working together. Thank you to my husband, Thomas, who is always so thoughtful about providing me the time, space, and support to do my work. This might be the only paper I ever publish. It took a village.

A Note from the Editor (Bowers)

There are two small but important pieces of additional context and consideration I would like to draw to the attention of readers.

To undiagnosed readers who connect with Dr. Norton's stories and who find themselves prompted to investigate the possibility that they may themselves be neurodivergent: First, let me briefly validate you and your journey and make sure you know that you are not alone. By virtue of the nature of Disability, neurodivergence, and the hegemony of eugenicist Ablism that underpins so many of the structures and ideologies we find ourselves ever swimming within, the subset of Neurodivergent people who successfully navigate the necessary gatekeepers in/to academia are disproportionately likely to be those with lower support needs (not necessarily low support needs, just lower than some of our peers) or whose support needs were invisibly fulfilled (e.g. through the power of Capital) who have managed to successfully navigate schooling and professional work sans diagnosis. Indeed, one of the main ways many in this subset might eventually come to recognize their own neurodivergence is through relating to the stories and experiences of others—if Dr. Norton's stories have prompted this sort of self-reflection in you, then you are in good company!

As you reflect on your own (possible) neurodivergence and the ways in which you do or don't relate to Dr. Norton's stories, you will of course want to look into ADHD, but you shouldn't limit yourself to that. Neurodivergence is prismatically variable in how it is experienced and externalized, but it is also often more than one thing. The comorbidity rate between ADHD and Autism has been estimated in ranges spanning from 30% to 70% (I, for example, have both). Dr. Norton's stories here *are* consistent with ADHD, but they're also consistent with AuDHD. If you relate and find yourself prompted to think more deeply about your own potential neurodivergence, consider investigating both ADHD and Autism (and their overlap). Indeed, don't limit yourself to those two possibilities. Treat them only as a pragmatic starting point.

To readers who might note that the font for this article is different than the font for other articles in the *Journal for Theoretical and Marginal Mathematics Education*: As a publication outlet, we deeply value criticality and (re)centering the margins vis-à-vis

messaging and meaning-making. These values are not limited to content, extending (as they necessarily do) to form. The font we typically use is Garamond but, per Dr. Norton's request, we are instead publishing this piece in Calibri. Why? Because it aligns with the messaging and meaning being conveyed by this piece. A common comorbidity with ADHD and several other spectra of Neurodivergence is dyslexia (indeed, this is a component of my own neurodivergence). For folk with dyslexia, it becomes particularly important to consider font choice, as some fonts are easier for us to parse. In general, this trends towards sans serif fonts with relatively large spacing. Calibri is an example of one of the more oft recommended fonts for authors trying to make their work accessible to dyslexic readers—it's inclusion here comprises a personal tribute from Dr. Norton to her time at Landmarks College *and* a broader (re)centering of the margins, and specifically Neurodivergence.

References

- Barnes, M. A., Martinez-Lopez, A., & Raghobar, K. P. (2017). Mathematical learning disabilities: What does the science tell us about assessment and diagnosis? *Perspectives on Language and Literacy*, 43(1), 10–19.
- Canela, C., Buadze, A., Dube, A., Eich, D., & Liebreuz, M. (2017). Skills and compensation strategies in adult ADHD: A qualitative study. *PLOS One*, 12(9), e1084964. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0184964>
- Cawley, A., & Wilson, R. (2023). Mathematical microaffirmations. *MAA Focus*, 43(6), 26–29.
- Chang, H. (2008). *Autoethnography as method*. Routledge.
- Denzin, N. K. (2013). *Interpretive autoethnography*. Sage Publications, Inc.
- Deshpande, S., Ostermeyer, B., & Lokhande, A. (2017). Managing adult attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder: To treat or not to treat? *Psychiatric Annals*, 47(6), 315–321. <https://doi.org/10.3928/00485713-20170515-01>
- Dolan, V. L. B. (2021). "...But if you tell anyone, I'll deny we ever met:" The experiences of academics with invisible disabilities in the neoliberal university. *International Journal of Qualitative Studies in Education*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09518398.2021.1885075>
- François-Sévigny, J., Pilon, M., & Gauthier, L.-A. (2022). Differences in parents and teachers' perceptions of behavior manifested by gifted children with ADHD compared to gifted children without ADHD and non-gifted children with ADHD using the Conners 3 Scale. *Brain Sciences*, 12(11), 1571. <https://doi.org/10.3390/brainsci12111571>
- Hedge, B. (2024). Persistence of STEM majors in higher education. *Journal of Research in Science, Mathematics and Technology Education*, 7(SI), 27–41. <https://doi.org/10.31756/jrsmte.312SI>
- Holthe, M. E. G., & Langvik, E. (2017). The strives, struggles, and successes of women diagnosed with ADHD as adults. *SAGE Open*, 7(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244017701799>

- Huynh, G., Mohsin, H., & Daniyan, A. (2024). The impact of late ADHD diagnosis on mental health outcomes in females. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 10.
- Kanu, Y., & Glor, M. (2006). “Currere” to the rescue? Teachers as “amateur intellectuals” in a knowledge society. *Journal of the Canadian Association for Curriculum Studies*, 4(2), 101–122. <https://doi.org/10.25071/1916-4467.17007>
- Lambert, R. (2024). *Rethinking disability and mathematics*. Corwin.
- Matthews, J. S., Gray, D. L., Lachaud, Q., McElveen, T. L., Chen, X., Victor, T., Okai, E., Boomhower, K., Wu, J., & Cha, E. (2021). *Belonging-centered instruction: An observational approach toward establishing inclusive mathematics classrooms*. <https://doi.org/10.31219/osf.io/n7bv2>
- Ng, Q. X., Ho, C. Y. X., Chan, H. W., Yong, B. Z. J., & Yeo, W. (2017). Managing childhood and adolescent attention-deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) with exercise: A systematic review. *Complementary Therapies in Medicine*, 34, 123–128. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ctim.2017.08.018>
- Poulos, C. (2021). *Essentials of autoethnography*. American Psychological Association.
- Pratchett, T. (2003). The wee free men. In *Tiffany Aching: Complete collection* (First Harper paperback edition on Kindle, pp. 2–266). HarperCollins.
- Pratchett, T. (2005). A hat full of sky. In *Tiffany Aching: Complete collection* (First Harper edition on Kindle, pp. 267–573). HarperCollins.
- Pratchett, T. (2007). Wintersmith. In *Tiffany Aching: Complete collection* (First paperback edition on Kindle, pp. 574–892). HarperCollins.
- Pratchett, T. (2011). I Shall Wear Midnight. In *Tiffany Aching: Complete collection* (First paperback edition on Kindle, pp. 893–1261). HarperCollins.
- Pratchett, T. (2015). The shepherd’s crown. In *Tiffany Aching: Complete collection* (First edition on Kindle, pp. 1262–1593). HarperCollins.
- Reinholz, D. (2023). *Equitable and engaging mathematics teaching: A guide to disrupting hierarchies in the classroom*. MAA Press.
- Sander-Williams, H. (2024). The experience of coaching for women with a late diagnosis of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder (ADHD). *International Journal of Evidence Based Coaching and Mentoring*, 18, 32–35. <https://doi.org/10.24384/2d3j-1c94>
- Schippers, L. M., Greven, C. U., & Hoogman, M. (2024). Associations between ADHD traits and self-reported strengths in the general population. *Comprehensive Psychiatry*, 130, 152461. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.comppsy.2024.152461>.
- Skolnick, J. F. (2023). *Gifted and distractable*. TarcherPerigee.
- Swick-Jemison, J. (2023). ADHD and the early career teaching librarian: An autoethnography. *Canadian Journal of Academic Librarianship*, 9, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.33137/cjal-rcbu.v9.40953>

Whipple, K. (2023). A story of mathematics and sports: Significant events in the evolution of a trans man. *Journal for Theoretical & Marginal Mathematics Education*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10073612>